

Floodwater ammoniacal-N (g/m^3)

2. Effect of floodwater depth on ammoniacal-N concentration in the water. Ludhiana, India.

intervals using a manifold and estimated by absorbing in 2% boric acid-mixed indicator solution. Floodwater samples also were analyzed for ammoniacal- and urea-N.

Floodwater depth significantly affected rate of NH_3 volatilization in flooded Ludhiana soil (Fig. 1). At 4 d after application, 1.8% of added urea was volatilized in 25-mm-deep water, but only a trace was volatilized in deeper water. At 11 d, NH_3 volatilization was 7.5, 4.5, 1.8, and 0.5% of added urea in 25, 50, 100, and 125 mm-deep-water, respectively.

Ammoniacal-N concentration in the floodwater 4 d after urea application was greatest at 25-mm-deep water and least at 125 mm (Fig. 2). □

Efficiency of modified nitrogen fertilizers in rice on partially reclaimed saline soil

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We compared sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and prilled urea (PU) at 0, 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg

Table 1. Effect of source and rate of N on grain yield of rice. Dalipnagar, India, 1982-83 wet season.

N (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
	PU	USG	SCU	Mean
0	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.5
29	2.0	2.3	2.4	2.2
58	2.5	2.8	2.8	2.7
87	2.9	3.2	3.2	3.1
116	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.4
Mean	2.5	2.7	2.7	

LSD (0.05) 0.187

N/ha in rice on partially reclaimed saline soil at the Dalipnagar research farm during 1982-83 wet season.

Experimental soil was loamy with pH 8.7, EC 183 dS/m at 25 °C, 0.039% total N, 135-8-214 available NPK/ha.

Treatments were PU best split, USG deep placed (10-12 cm soil depth) 1 wk after transplanting Jaya variety, and

Composting with rice straw

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Rice straw is an important source of organic matter in rice-growing areas, but applying it directly into soil has a number of limitations. Composting appears to be an alternative.

Composting originated in upland cropping areas, where the basic raw materials are crop stovers other than rice straw and farmyard manure (primarily horse manure). We tested composting with rice straw and pig manure (pigs are the basic livestock in rice-growing areas in China).

The essential factors for composting were defined as optimal C:N ratio of around 40 in raw materials; chopped rice straw, mixed with grasses and leguminous leaves or tender tips, if available; pig manure or other farmyard manure; superphosphate at 3% of total raw material weight; appropriate moisture and aeration conditions.

The temperature at the center of the pile was raised to 70 °C across 34 d,

Table 2. Influence of source and N rate on N recovery.

N (kg/ha)	N recovery (%)			
	PU	USG	SCU	Mean
29	42.86	63.21	69.28	58.45
58	40.10	54.30	55.75	50.05
87	39.00	46.75	47.60	44.45
116	37.00	41.55	42.15	40.23
Mean	39.74	51.45	53.69	

SCU broadcast and incorporated at transplanting. P and K were applied uniformly at 26-25 kg/ha. ZnSO_4 was applied to the nursery bed at 25 kg/ha.

SCU and USG were significantly superior to PU at all N levels (Table 1), with a greater difference at lower N levels.

N recovery was highest with SCU (Table 2). Recovery of N decreased linearly with increase in N level. □

maintained for about 1 wk, then dropped gradually (see figure). Superphosphate showed some effect on keeping temperatures high, resulting in better compost maturity. Composting was completed in 45 to 60 d when N content was 0.3-0.4% and C:N ratio was 20.

The compost was used as basal manure for double-cropped rice. Table 1 gives the recovery of nutrients, Table 2 shows effect of rice straw compost on yield. Yields with rice straw compost were comparable to yield with conventional manure.

Temperature during composting. JAAS, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China.